

Science & TRUST

The microessay competition
THE WINNERS!

THE WINNERS OF THE CRASTINA "SCIENCE & TRUST" MICROESSAY COMPETITION 2020

We in The Crastina Crew are delighted to announce that The Crastina "Science and Trust" Microessay Competition 2020 has been completed and we are now ready to announce THE WINNERS across the two different categories: a public vote for the "People's Writer", and a jury selection.

Category 1: Vox populi - the voice of the people!

Following an intensive week of voting, we received 251 votes total and we are delighted to publicly announce the names of the "Writers of the People" :

FIRST PLACE

Prayan Pokharel

"Indeed, the main foundation of humanity relies on understanding the natural world. The global pandemic, COVID-19, is a lively example. Scientific knowledge belongs to society. This era has witnessed many scientific revolutions in the realm of communication, environment, health, and genomics. Trust in science differs depending on the society's educational, social, economic, political, religious and historical factors. In a society, people exist who argue not to trust science because scientists change their minds; actually, it is not about changing minds; it is about evolving knowledge with new evidence. Therefore, we need to understand that the research is progressive, and whatever it is now at a given moment will itself be debatable later on. For an example, it is surprisingly fast on the development of vaccines against coronavirus. We will never progress if we trust on everything. However, on scientific matters, society should trust science."

Hide entry

SECOND PLACE

Emilia Pasik

Show entry

THIRD PLACE

Chinmaya KV

Show entry

